

IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION ON INDIAN EDUCATION ECOSYSTEM AS A WHOLE

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Abstract:

When COVID-19 Pandemic hit our globe in 2019, it forced all the industries around the world to step in for its online presence. Unlike other industries in India, Education sector was hesitant to digitalization, however COVID-19 Pandemic forced it into the transformation. This transformation took everyone by surprise with no other option left. This paper discusses this transformation of Indian Education Ecosystem, its advantages, disadvantages on all the involved stakeholders of the ecosystem. It further elaborates on the challenges it has faced so far and still facing while providing recommendations for making this digitalization a success in the long run!

Key words:

Digitalization: *to be operated with the use of computers and the internet.*

Digitization: *the conversion of text, pictures, or sound into a digital form*

Ecosystem: *interconnected system.*

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Introduction:

Digitalization in very broad manner refers to “the adoption or increase in use of digital or computer technology by an organization, industry or a country”. Computer technology was introduced in India roughly in year 1995. Since then, many organizations started shifting to computer technology for its day to day operations. The IT sector in India was born in 1967 in Mumbai with establishment of the TATA CONSULTANCY SERVICES by the TATA GROUP. Yet the use of Computer technology across all sectors was limited to manging the business operations or the organizational process, i.e. data entry,

accounting, record keeping, etc.

It was now in 20's when few Ed-Tech Start-up's entered the Indian market with a vision of providing education online. While the Indian population was not ready to accept the technology in the educational sector, COVID-19 Pandemic left the world with no choice but to switch on to the online learning methods. While platforms like YouTube were widely used as a non-conventional means of learning, such platforms were not widely used and completely relied on for teaching and learning processes.

With rise and partial decline of COVID-19 Pandemic across the globe including India, Education Technology industry has gained significant popularity in India with many Start-up's and Unicorns trying to generalize the Technology and create awareness about its benefits. However, no technology comes without challenges and disadvantages which has not been different for Online Education either.

This paper elaborates on the changes Indian Education Ecosystem has undergone while transforming itself into a partially successful Online Education Ecosystem in the times of COVID-19 Pandemic. It further also discusses the advantages, disadvantages and challenges it has addressed and yet to be addressed.

Indian Education Ecosystem:

Both Government and Private institutions provides significant contribution to the Indian Education Ecosystem. It offers a very wide range of learning opportunities to its geographically and socially diverse population. The learning or teaching pattern of most of the service providers in this industry is largely based on theoretical knowledge while a significant number of stakeholders are shifting towards global methods lately. Lectures or Classes are important components of the Learning process in India and it also consumes the most time of learning / study hours of the students. Discussion and brain storming sessions along with practical learning session are gaining position in the learning process; however, the use of such processes needs to be increased in the learning processes.

One can easily understand the complexity of the Indian Education Ecosystem after reviewing its geographical distribution, domain wise distribution, its admission and fees structure, etc. There are two different terminologies when it comes to use of Technology in Educational sector. The first one being digitization which has largely affected the administration process of the ecosystem like record keeping, data collection, data processing, etc; while the other being digitalization which refers to the use of technology

for learning and teaching process. In this paper we will be majorly focusing on the Digitalization of the Indian Education Ecosystem.

Objectives

1. Discussing the Digitalization process of the Indian Education Ecosystem
2. Discussing impact of Digitalization on the Indian Education Ecosystem
3. Discussing the challenges and Solutions of the Digitalization

5 Components Model of the Indian Education Ecosystem:

The diagram above showcases the five main components of the Indian Education Ecosystem that has direct or indirect effects on one or all of the stake holders of this system considering students, Teachers, Non-teaching staff, Government regulators all as the stakeholders of this ecosystem. Further part of the papers discusses in depth about how each component affects students, staff and administrative staff where applicable.

Learning Process

When the COVID-19 Pandemic paved way for online lectures the life of students and teachers both changed drastically. After talking to many students and teachers from different levels of educational institutes and making personal surveys, below are some of the findings:

For Students:

1. Due to online lecture, much time was saved by students needed for travelling to institutions leaves excess time available in their hands to be utilized for other productive purposes.
2. Recordings of online lectures also saved time of students needed for taking notes and efforts needed to preserve those bulky paper sheets or notes.

3. As students started submitting assignments online, a sizable cost for marginal and poor students was saved on stationary where pages of written assignments were demanded.
4. No restriction on location also facilitated some rural students to save accommodation cost and contribute in their daily family work of farming or of similar kind.
5. Many students on a positive note also stated that online lectures also encouraged them to learn new technologies useful in their daily life like online payments, YouTube for educational purposes, word, excel, etc.
6. Many students hope the software's they learned like Microsoft office, Zoom Meetings, Gmail boosted their knowledge and experience with the technology and will help them in the long run.
7. For a number of students, coming from rural or semi urban background, software like Gmail, Zoom Meetings, Google Classrooms were not known. They faced problems in joining the online lectures, accessing different functions of the online lectures.
8. For few unfortunate poor students, means of online education such as mobile phones, laptops, tablets were unavailable due to poor financial status.
9. Many rural students lacked proper internet facility and mobile network coverage in their rural homes. Many faced issued of electricity load shading. For most of the students, language barrier created obstacles while accessing the technology forcing them to perform poor in their overall academics.
10. If one has to talk about nursery, pre-primary and primary levels of educations, online education is so far a complete failure due to number of reasons such as children of those age are unable to use mobile phones or laptops, children felt bored attending the online lectures and had to be accompanys by an adult continuously, etc.

For Teachers / Lecturers:

1. Online teaching methods were completely unknown to the experienced and near retirement teachers.
2. For most of the teachers, online teaching was challenging while ensuring each student understands the subject.
3. It was also difficult for teachers to track each and every student's contribution in classes, if students are attentive or not, and his/her performance through online systems.
4. Many teachers themselves were not aware or familiar with technologies such as

Gmail, Zoom Meetings, Google Classrooms, etc.

5. Many teachers lacked the skills for using the programs such as Microsoft Word, PowerPoint, Excel efficiently. Due to this many struggled to meet the time deadlines for their assigned task.
6. Almost all of the female teachers struggled maintaining a balance between domestic work and professional work while in “work from home” with increased expectations from family members and all the family members being home throughout the day. They found it hard to complete their professional tasks in time while completing their daily domestic chores.
7. While most of the teachers were familiar with WhatsApp, they lack the knowledge of integrating different technologies for accomplishing a same task such as ‘scheduling a meeting’.
8. Teachers belonging to the rural areas of the country faced problems associated with unavailability of proper teaching instruments such as laptops, WIFI or internet facility, etc.
9. Most teachers were unknown of how to take online exams. Very few of teachers knew how to record and track students’ performances using excel or similar softwares.
10. Most of the teachers faced problems in giving assignments and collecting assignments from students.
11. Several times, teachers also found out students using technology to cheat in exams. On several occasions students made excuses of unavailability of proper internet or facilities essential to complete assignments of attend lectures making it hard for teachers to implement general rules of institutions like attendance for such class of students.
12. When most of the institutions instructed teachers to provide students with teaching or explanation videos, provide them with online notes, most of the teachers lacks both efficiency and skills to complete such tasks.
13. For some teachers, the inputs demanded for online teaching exerted mental pressure on them specially for older teachers or with teachers with no facilities available create a tensed work environment for them. Such incidents drastically impacted the efficiency of learning process.

Communication and Sharing:

Unlike for other processes, online education brought about some very positive changes

in the ecosystem. During personal survey, both the teachers as well as students reacted positively and agreed that online technology helped them in better communication and sharing of academic materials.

1. For students obtaining, sharing and storing of notes became way easier through online means and electronic storages.
2. Platforms like WhatsApp, Google classrooms helped both teachers and students to convey any notice or message to a large number of groups through one click.
3. Creating and distributing academic material became more easier for teachers with proper and skilful use of technology
4. Through platforms like Google Classrooms, it was becoming easier for teachers to share academic material with one click ensuring no student is left out.
5. For many marginal and poor students, the cost of Xeroxing notes and study materials reduced drastically.
6. Electronic communications and sharing also promoted exchange of material among teachers of different institutions belong to different geographical locations promoting sense of perfection and upgradation in the notes created by them.
7. Technology based sharing and communications also paved way for both teachers and students to acquire out of the box knowledge and disseminate it further within their circles.
8. Getting used to the online education technology also promoted culture of online conferences and paper presentations providing more exposure to both students and teachers nationally and internationally.

Social Engagement:

Online Education has not been revolutionary in every component of Educational Ecosystem and unfortunately Social Engagement was one of them as found in the personal Surveys. Online Education has drastically reduced the social contact between student as well as teachers.

1. It is view of most of the teachers that online education has impacted primary students in a very negative way when it comes to socialization. It has been their observation that such students are shy in their social life. They lack stage daring and tend to communicate less in public.
2. Teachers also mentioned that few students are not active during online lecturing and do not speak up about their problems making it challenging for them to understand the

proper level of their class and design teaching modules accordingly.

3. Primary level students were unable to enjoy the school hours with friends. For several students, this made learning for them less fun and they felt attending school as boredom.
4. For higher level students, due to online learning, there were no academic discussions any more. Many students complained of missing an important step in learning through discussions during their online lectures.
5. Many students mentioned about missing out opportunity to create new connections and gained both social and academic exposure through connections. Many students mentioned that socialization was one of the ways for them to build their career and choose career paths.
6. Apart from students, teachers also mentioned facing problems of coordination and cooperation amongst themselves. With work from home, the social essence of friendship and association amongst the teachers started weakening. The gap between hierarchy levels amongst the staff members started widening.

Ecosystem Efficiency:

This part of the report comments on how Digitalization changes professional lives of specially the non – teaching and also the teaching staff of the Indian Education Ecosystem.

1. Digitalization was partially beneficial for not only teachers and students but also for the administrative staff of the Educational Institutes.
2. Digitization and Digitalization both shifted many offline administrative processes to online methods. Both Government and Private Institutes developed portals for conducting administrative processes online.
3. Shifting of admission, fees collection and record keeping methods to online modes not only reduces the efforts of administrative staff needed in handling the huge paper trials for such processes, but it also facilitated speed in such processes.
4. Online methods are faster and easier to maintain and modify as mentioned by the non – teaching faculties of the different educational institutions. The chances of missing a record, or misplacing a record are far more less in online mode as compared to the offline mode.
5. Online submission of documents made it easier for students, teachers as well as administrative staff. Furthermore, online communication helped the non-teaching staff

save time and expenditure required for physically transporting the documents to appropriate authorities for admissions, fees payments, appointments, etc.

6. While many non-teaching staff also mentioned the tremendous troubles, they faced while learning the new system, most of them favours online technology for such works mentioning reasons such as its faster, required less efforts, helps in eradicating corrupt practices and increasing the transparency in the system.

Efficiency and Resource Utilization:

It is no surprise that online technology has helped industries cut their daily expenditure by significant values, it also has potential to help educational sector cut its costs drastically and make education even more affordable to every interested candidate. While it may have some notable negative effects on the ecosystem as a whole, below discussed is the scope online system will provide to the Ecosystem:

1. Online lectures eradicate the need for huge infrastructure in schools and higher education institutes. These costs saved in infrastructure can make Education very affordable to common man in long run.
2. Online Education ecosystem will facilitate employers to saves costs on paying Travel and Dining allowances to its staff which will indirectly lower the cost of education for common people.
3. Online processes have also facilitated optimum utilization of teaching resources such as online notes, educational videos, etc and have saved recurring expenses on its recreation.
4. Online processes have dramatically increased the speed at which ecosystem functions making it friendlier for all involved stakeholders.

Challenges:

1. Except from the urban population, still a huge chunk of rural population lack access to instruments of online education such as mobile phones, laptops, Wi-fi, etc.
2. Most of the rural population is not financially capable of making investments in costly mobile phones, laptops and other facilities essential for online education.
3. The increasing costs of internet recharge is creating new challenge for economically poor and marginal students.
4. Currently, most of the technology is accessible only in English language. This further creates language barrier to socio academically backward students as well as teachers.
5. Most of teachers in this ecosystem are old and are near to their retirement. For such

staff it is difficult to learn with technology and skills required for online teaching.

6. Online lectures are not much engaging and during such lecture it is difficult to tract contributions of each student in case of classes where number of students are more. Such conditions are resulting in academic losses of students.
7. Significant population of teachers do not possess knowledge to utilize the technologies available for online teaching purposes.
8. Online examinations are easier to cheat in and this creates challenges for authorities for fair and equal evaluation and competition among students.
9. Online learning can be boring and loose interest of some students if not done in proper way resulting in academic losses of the students.
10. Besides technical difficulties, online learning can also be hazardous for health and make students less active.

Conclusion:

After making many personal interviews and surveys, considering opinions of many experienced people from the sector a conclusion can be drawn that online education can be very promising if utilized in well-structured manner. Based on the findings from this paper, I have proposed some structured changes to make online learning an efficient and effective process for all involved stake holders:

1. Need for Government to draw strategies to ensure all the students and teachers can obtain all the necessary facilities, tools and instruments for online learning & teaching.
2. Institutions should provide skill enhancement trainings to both its teachers and students to ensure them possess knowledge for optimum utilization of all the technology essential for online teaching as well as learning.
3. There is need to provide teachers with easy to use tools and instruments for creation of teaching material which is more understandable to students.
4. Innovative teaching methods are needed to be drawn up by integrating the teachers from different domains.
5. As online education negatively impacts the socialization skills of involved stakeholders, a weekly or monthly physical meeting / presentations / discussion sessions should be compulsorily introduced in the learning processes.
6. Considering the overall growth of students and staff, practical sessions should be introduced in the learning process which will enable students to gain practical

knowledge and experience.

7. Technology keeps evolving every day. That is why it is of utmost importance for the ecosystem to adopt practises that will keep all its stake holders' updates.
8. Online education does not encourage social networking through offline means, therefore it is of utmost importance that the institutions also focus on teaching its stake holders skills required for online networking which will help them in building their career.
9. The ecosystem should also focus on the neglected areas of online education system such as soft skills development, body language learning, in person communication skills, presentation skills, public speaking skills, etc.
10. The ecosystem should adopt practises to continue various offline activities such as speech competitions, sports, debates, etc. Such activities have proved to be of immense importance in social, physical, mental and interpersonal development of students.
11. The ecosystem should introduce different platforms and sessions to promote healthy academic discussions, brain storming sessions and innovation activities which are key to develop skilled human resources for social as well as national growth.
12. The ecosystem should continue festive celebrations, anniversary celebrations of leaders who has shaped our country in a way that students keeps learning and encouraging from them in a way similar to offline school events.
13. Ecosystem should ensure fair evaluation of all the student by avoiding cheating by use of unfair means during online learning processes.
14. The ecosystem should identify and utilize the scope of online learning and make its structures use in constantly upgrading the syllabus, teaching methods and subjects.

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